

THE COMPARISON OF BIOCELLULOSE WOUND DRESSING AND NORMAL SALINE DRESSING IN THE PROCESS OF WOUND HEALING IN MICE SKIN

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ABSTRACT Loss of skin integrity and continuity as a result of injury may cause a non-healing chronic wound. After the injury, sequences of wound healing phases are set in motion to accomplish tissue repair. Neutrophils infiltration in the inflammatory phase can protect the host from infection and secrete enzymes which cause tissue damage. Current view of wound healing modalities generally requires the materials to enhance epidermal regeneration. Normal saline wound dressings are commonly used in clinical practices. The search for the ideal wound dressing material is continuing. Recently, biocellulose, also known as bacterial cellulose has been developed for wound dressing. Biocellulose wound dressings (BWD) have been shown to be effective in the treatment of chronic non-healing wounds due to its ability to both donate and absorb moisture.

This study was an experimental animal study with a control group to determine the effect of biocellulose nata de coco as a wound dressing in mice by assessing the wound diameter and the amounts of neutrophils. Fifty standardized female albino mice were divided into 3 groups based on the intervention; control group (n=20), NaCl 0.9% group (n=15), and biocellulose group (n=15). Each group was then terminated in the following days; 3rd day, 7th day, and 14th day. Punch biopsy of the back was performed to assess the changes in diameter, and histopathological examination was done to assess the neutrophil count. The results indicated a significantly smaller diameter and reduced mean neutrophil count in the biocellulose group. This experimental animal study demonstrated that BWD is significantly superior to normal saline dressing in promoting wound healing.

KEYWORDS biocellulose, wound dressing, normal saline, wound healing

Introduction

The skin has its primary function to serve as a protective barrier against the environment. Loss of skin integrity and continuity as a result of injury may cause non-healing chronic wound which could lead to significant disability. Wound healing is a

complex process which requires the involvement of many different tissues, cell types and matrix components. [1] After wound injury, sequences of wound healing phases are set in motion to accomplish tissue repair which includes the inflammatory phase, proliferative phase and remodelling phase. [2] Starting within minutes after injury, neutrophils are thought to protect the host from infection and secrete enzymes which cause tissue damage. Subsequently, the resolution of inflammation is often delayed and results in non-healing wounds. [3] Multiple factors have been hypothesized to associated with wound stagnation, including the presence of biofilm, necrotic tissue, compromised circulation, and prolonged pressure. [4]

Current view of wound healing modalities generally requires the wound dressing to create an optimal environment for epidermal regeneration and provide a barrier against wound infection

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Table 1 Wound mean diameter

Group	Wound mean diameter (mm)				p* value
	1st day termination (n=5)	3rd day termination (n=5)	7th day termination (n=5)	14th day termination (n=5)	
Control (n=20)	6.0	4.6	4.0	2.0	<0.001
NaCl 0.9% (n=15)		4.8	4.2	2.2	<0.001
Biocellulose (n=15)		3.2	2.4	0.2	<0.001
p* value		<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	
Kruskal Wallis					

Table 2 Wound mean diameter

Group	Wound mean diameter (mm)		
	3rd day termination (n=5)	7th day termination (n=5)	14th day termination (n=5)
NaCl 0.9% (n=15)	4.8	4.2	2.2
Biocellulose (n=15)	3.2	2.4	0.2
p* value	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05
Post-hoc analysis			

as well as preventing excessive fluid loss. Many different biological and synthetic wound dressings have been developed to promote wound healing. Normal saline wound dressings are commonly used in clinical practices as it is considered cheap and easy to apply. However, a search for the ideal wound dressing material is continuing. In the field of wound healing, an ideal wound dressing must demonstrate similarity to both structurally and functionally autograft skin. [1] Recently, biocellulose also known as bacterial cellulose has been developed for several purposes, including wound dressing. [5] Biocellulose wound dressings (BWD) have been shown to be effective in the treatment of chronic non-healing wounds due to its ability to both donate and absorb moisture. [6] Other than its mechanical properties, biocellulose is also thought to be similar to human skin which allows the growth, spreading, and migration of human keratinocytes. [7] In animal studies, BWD was shown to enhance the healing of acute partial thickness wounds. [8]

Methods

This study was an experimental animal study with a control group to determine the effect of biocellulose nata de coco as a wound dressing in mice by assessing the wound diameter and the number of neutrophils. This study was conducted in the animal laboratory division and pathology anatomy division of Faculty of Medicine Hasanuddin University, Makassar, Indone-

sia, during June 2016 with ethics committee of Health Research approval.

The sample of this study was 50 healthy non-pregnant female albino mice aged 10-12 weeks with an average weight of 20-30 grams obtained from Laboratory of Research and Development Maros. Mice were maintained for one week in standardised conditions: temperature $24\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$, humidity $50\pm 10^{\circ}\text{C}$, and room brightness with light/dark cycle interval for 12 hours.

Fifty female albino mice were divided into 3 groups based on the intervention; control group (n=20), NaCl 0.9% group (n=15), and biocellulose group (n=15), of which then each group was divided with interval termination day; 3rd day, 7th day, and 14th day, with each group consisted of 5 mice and addition of 1st day termination (n=5) only in control group. Six mm punch biopsy of the back was performed to create a subcutaneous wound which further assessed for the changes in diameter after given each intervention once daily. Histopathological examination using Hematoxylin-Eosin staining was done at each interval termination day to identify the number of neutrophils based on the mean of 3 random visual fields ($50\times 100\mu\text{m}$) evaluation with $40\times$ magnification using microscopy (Olympus® DP12).

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS statistics program (SPSS 17 Inc. Chicago, IL, USA). Differences between the variables were evaluated using the Kruskal-Wallis test followed by post-hoc analysis to evaluate differences between two variables. Analysis was presented in the form of tables with descriptions.

Results

The results indicated a significantly smaller diameter ($p<0.001$) in biocellulose group than the other two groups, with lesser diameter shown as the longer the mice terminated (Table 1). The differences of wound mean diameter between NaCl 0.9% and biocellulose group was considered significant ($p<0.05$), correspondingly between control group dan biocellulose group (Table 2). Mean neutrophil count per visual field among three groups also proven significant ($p<0.001$) with substantial neutrophil count differences between control and biocellulose group (Table 3). Noted the decreased mean neutrophil count with longer termination day, particularly the significant differences between NaCl 0.9% and biocellulose group ($p<0.05$) (Table 4).

Table 3 Mean neutrophil count/ visual field

Group	Mean neutrophil count/ visual field				p* value
	1st day termination (n=5)	3rd day termination (n=5)	7th day termination (n=5)	14th day termination (n=5)	
Control (n=20)	41.1	108.3	96.1	31.4	<0.001
NaCl 0.9% (n=15)		90.7	75.3	28.2	<0.001
Biocellulose (n=15)		11.7	3.4	2.0	<0.001
p* value		<0.05	<0.05	<0.05	
Kruskal Wallis					

Table 4 Mean neutrophil count/ visual field

Group	Mean neutrophil count/ visual field		
	3rd day termination (n=5)	7th day termination (n=5)	14th day termination (n=5)
NaCl 0.9% (n=15)	90.7	75.3	28.2
Biocellulose (n=15)	11.7	3.4	2.0
p* value	<0.05	<0.05	<0.05
Post-hoc analysis			

Discussion

This experimental animal study was done to compare the effect of once-daily biocellulose nata de coco wound dressing and normal saline dressing (NaCl 0.9%), by assessing the wound diameter and the amounts of neutrophils. The results indicated a significantly smaller diameter and reduced mean neutrophil count in biocellulose group compared to normal saline group and control group.

Nata de coco is cellulose formed by fermentation using coconut water, where nata or also known as bacterial cellulose is white gelatinous cellulose which is produced from fermentation of *Acetobacter aceti* ssp. *xylinum* using fruit juices medium. [9] Nata has high fibre content, low calorific value and high water content which exceeds 90%. [10] The previous study reported that film produced by *Acetobacter aceti* ssp *xylinum* contained water and cellulose as the main component. [11] Whereas, normal saline wound dressings are commonly used in clinical practices as an adjunct in the treatment of open wounds since it is considered cheap and easy to apply. The hypothesis that dressings have the osmotic capacity through evaporation of water that makes the dressing hypertonic and provides a moist environment for its physiologically normal and isotonic properties. [12]

After wound injury, sequences of wound healing phases are set in motion culminating in tissue repair. Three well-described

overlapping phases are inflammatory phase followed by proliferative phase and remodelling phase. [2] As part of the inflammatory phase, massive infiltration of neutrophils into the subepidermal region of the wound bed is most significant at first-day post-injury. Starting within minutes after injury, neutrophils are thought to protect the host from infection by combating an invading microorganism and clearing cellular debris. During this process, activated neutrophils secrete a battery of bioactive substances, such as proteases and reactive oxygen intermediates, which can lead to severe tissue damage. This is most clearly demonstrated in non-healing wounds where the resolution of inflammation is often delayed. [3]

The acceleration of wound healing of BWD is thought as a result of the moisturized wound and minimized maceration as the excess exudate and toxins removed from the wound. Also, oxygens can permeate more through the dressing to improve cells regeneration. [13] Biocellulose is considered as an ideal material for the healing of high exudate wound for it has an ultrafine network with high porosity which allows a high capability for water uptake. The highly uniaxial oriented nanofibers of biocellulose contribute to a high crystallinity content, providing impressive mechanical strength for better controlling the wet state. Also, the water retention characteristic of biocellulose creates a moist wound healing environment, which allows for faster healing than a drier environment. [5],[14],[15] Furthermore, a multicenter randomised prospective study on venous leg ulcers patients using BWD stated that based on their experience, biocellulose is effective on mild exuding ulcers, where dressing changes can be performed up to once weekly. [16] Another study also stated that neutrophils might provide protection against infection but also retard wound closure, elucidated from significantly improved epidermal healing measured by faster wound closure in neutropenic mice. [3] This study highlights the superiority of BWD compared with normal saline dressing in mice skin based on the smaller wound diameter and reduced neutrophilic infiltration which more significantly presented at a longer healing time. Further detailed study with more parameter substantial in the process of wound healing is necessary for aiming to generate clinical trial.

Conclusion

This experimental animal study demonstrated that BWD is significantly superior to normal saline dressing in promoting wound healing.

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